

Motion of Fluid Around a Solid Sphere

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Summary

The steady laminar flow around a submerged sphere was investigated theoretically with the Navier-Stokes equations. Instead of the infinite fluid of classical studies, a series solution was successfully developed for a fluid having a uniform velocity at a fixed distance from the sphere.

The solution is complete, allowing the calculation of all properties of interest within the bounds of its physical assumptions and the limitations of the series method. When extrapolated to an infinite fluid it is consistent with Stokes law and the classical creeping flow equations. This series solution, however, does not converge at high flow velocities, in particular at Reynolds numbers where a wake is known to be present. It provides though the prediction of the absence of a wake at sufficiently low Reynolds numbers.

1. Physical Model

Instead of an infinite fluid, a physically realizable situation was adopted. It assumes a stationary solid sphere is submerged in fluid that moves with a uniform velocity at all the points on an imaginary spherical surface concentric with the solid sphere. The fluid not on the imaginary spherical surface is unconstrained. Figure 1 depicts the model and the coordinate system used.

Fig. 1. Coordinate system [1] and physical model.

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The coordinate system and notation are identical to those of Bird, Stewart and Lightfoot [1] in their description of the classical problem. Spherical coordinates r, θ, ϕ are used, with Cartesian coordinates x, y, z also depicted for reference. Axial symmetry is assumed about the z -axis ($\theta=0, \pi$), with no dependencies on ϕ or time.

The solid sphere of radius R is surrounded by a Newtonian fluid of constant density ρ and viscosity μ . Concentric with the sphere there is an imaginary spherical surface of radius A such that the fluid at every point on this imaginary spherical surface has a uniform velocity V in the direction of the coordinate axis z . There are no other constraints on the fluid.

1.1. Relationships

With the formulation of Bird, Stewart and Lightfoot [1], the fluid behavior is described by the stream function ψ and the following relationships, taken directly from that work:

$$v_r = -\frac{1}{r^2 \sin\theta} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\theta} \quad (1)$$

$$v_\theta = +\frac{1}{r \sin\theta} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial r} \quad (2)$$

$$vE^4\psi = \frac{1}{r^2 \sin\theta} \frac{\partial(\psi, E^2\psi)}{\partial(r, \theta)} - \frac{2E^2\psi}{r^2 \sin^2\theta} \left(\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial r} \cos\theta - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\theta} \sin\theta \right) \quad (3)$$

where

$$v = \frac{\mu}{\rho} \quad (4a)$$

$$E^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{\sin\theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} \left(\frac{1}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta} \right) \quad (4b)$$

$$E^4\psi = E^2(E^2\psi) \quad (4c)$$

$$\frac{\partial(f, g)}{\partial(x, y)} = \begin{vmatrix} \partial f/\partial x & \partial f/\partial y \\ \partial g/\partial x & \partial g/\partial y \end{vmatrix} \quad (4d)$$

1.2. Boundary Conditions

There are four boundary conditions to be satisfied:

1. The sphere is solid and the fluid does not permeate it:

$$v_r = 0 \text{ at } r = R, \text{ or the equivalent } \psi = C_1, \text{ a constant, at } r = R \quad (5a)$$

2. No slip of the fluid at the sphere surface

$$v_\theta = 0 \text{ at } r = R, \text{ or the equivalent } \partial\psi/\partial r = 0 \text{ at } r = R \quad (5b)$$

3, 4. At the imaginary sphere the velocity equals V and is in the direction of the z -axis ($\theta = 0$):

$$v_r = V \cos\theta, \text{ which integrates into } \psi = -\frac{1}{2} A^2 \sin^2\theta + C_2, \text{ a constant, at } r = A \quad (5c)$$

$$v_\theta = -V \sin\theta \text{ at } r = A, \text{ which transforms into } \partial\psi/\partial r = -VA \sin^2\theta \text{ at } r = A \quad (5d)$$

2. Series Solution

Equation 3 can be arranged with the Reynolds number at the right hand side, multiplying the higher order terms of the stream function as in:

$$E^4\psi = \left(\frac{\text{Re}}{2}\right) \times (\text{terms of order } \psi^2) \quad (6)$$

where the one-half fraction is used for convenience, and:

$$\frac{\text{Re}}{2} = \frac{RV\rho}{\mu} \quad (7)$$

The series solution centers on the expansion of the stream function in a power series of the form

$$\psi = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \psi_k \left(\frac{\text{Re}}{2}\right)^k \quad (8)$$

The first term, ψ_0 , would correspond to the creeping flow situation, and would be obtained from the equation:

$$E^4\psi_0 = 0 \quad (9)$$

Subsequent terms, for progressively higher powers of $(\text{Re}/2)$, would be obtained in a similar fashion from those already found, as in:

$$E^4\psi_k = \sum_{k_1=0}^{k-1} (\text{terms with } \psi_{k_1} \times \psi_{k-1-k_1}) \quad \text{for } k > 0 \quad (10)$$

A framework was devised that would allow the solution of these equations. Inspection of Eq. 3 reveals that a viable form for the stream function is:

$$\psi = VR^2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{n_L(k)} \sum_{j=0}^{j_L(k,n)} \sum_{i_F(k,n,j)}^{i_L(k,n,j)} b_{knji} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^i \left(\ln\frac{r}{R}\right)^j \cos^n\theta \sin^2\theta \left(\frac{\text{Re}}{2}\right)^k \quad (11)$$

where b_{knji} represent dimensionless constants that would depend on geometry. For consistency with having the stream function be zero along the z-axis ($\theta = 0, \pi$), integration constants C_1 and C_2 of Eqs. 5 are set as zero. The included summation limits are from insights gained during development: For each k there is a finite number of powers of $\cos\theta$. For each pair of k and n, j remains finite; and i has positive and negative values for all combinations of k, n , and j .

2.1. Procedure

Central to the procedure used is the behavior of the E^4 operator with the typical term of the series. When applied, the power of (r/R) is uniformly decreased by 4, while the highest powers of $\ln(r/R)$ and $\cos\theta$ are maintained:

$$\begin{aligned}
E^4 \left\{ \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^i \left(\ln \frac{r}{R} \right)^j \cos^n \theta \sin^2 \theta \right\} \\
= r^{i-4} \sin^2 \theta \left\{ (i-n-2)(i-n-4)(i+n+1)(i+n-1) \left(\ln \frac{r}{R} \right)^j \cos^n \theta \right. \\
\left. + j \left(\ln \frac{r}{R} \right)^{j-1} \cos^n \theta \dots + \dots \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

It is evident that for each power of $\cos \theta$ there are four special powers of (r/R) for which their contribution to the E^4 operator vanishes at any desired power of $\ln(r/R)$. These are:

$$i = n + 4; n + 2; -n + 1; -n - 1 \tag{13}$$

The coefficients associated with these powers of (r/R) serve to satisfy the boundary conditions.

When calculating a stream function component ψ_k from its E^4 expansion with the already-known lower order terms as in Eq. 10, we start from the highest power of $\cos \theta$ downwards, and find all coefficients for each power n in order. For a particular n we treat each power “ $i - 4$,” from the highest power j downwards. The corresponding coefficient b_{kni} can be calculated directly by dividing the term at the right hand side of Eq. 10 by the first factor in expansion 12. This fails however when i is one of the special values in Eq. 13, as a term at the right hand side of Eq. 10 cannot be produced by the first element in Eq. 12. That term is instead generated by the second element of a term with the next higher power of $\ln(r/R)$, i.e., $j + 1$, and is used to obtain the coefficient corresponding to that higher power. Incidentally, this is how logarithms are introduced into this solution.

The equation is then adjusted by including all the terms derived from the newly-found coefficients and the process repeated for lower powers of $\ln(r/R)$ until $j = 0$ (or $j=1$ for a special i) is reached for all the powers of (r/R) of the particular n . Only four coefficients are not known, corresponding to $j = 0$ and the four special powers of i in Eq. 13, and are obtained from the linear equations that result from the four boundary conditions applying to each pair of k and n :

From Eq. 5a:

$$\sum_i b_{k,n,j=0,i} = 0 \tag{14a}$$

From Eq. 5b:

$$\sum_i (i b_{k,n,j=0,i} + b_{k,n,j=1,i}) = 0 \tag{14b}$$

From Eq. 5c:

$$\sum_j \sum_i b_{k,n,j,i} \left(\frac{A}{R} \right)^i \left(\ln \frac{A}{R} \right)^j = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{A}{R} \right)^2 & \text{for } k = 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } k \geq 1 \end{cases} \tag{14c}$$

From Eq. 5d:

$$\sum_j \sum_i b_{k,n,j,i} \left(\frac{A}{R} \right)^{i-1} \left[i \left(\ln \frac{A}{R} \right)^j + j \left(\ln \frac{A}{R} \right)^{j-1} \right] = \begin{cases} -\frac{A}{R} & \text{for } k = 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } k \geq 1 \end{cases} \tag{14d}$$

Compensation for the newly found coefficients allow continuation of the calculations with Eq. 10 to progressively lower powers of $\cos \theta$ until all terms are accounted for.

2.2. Results

2.2.1. Creeping Flow

Eq. 9 describes the first term of the stream function series expansion, which is satisfied by $n = 0$, and $i = 4, 2, 1, -1$. It should be mentioned that these four powers of (r/R) have been associated previously with creeping flow, but the highest power 4 has uniformly been dismissed in the classical treatments that adopt the view that the maximum power should be 2 to have uniform flow at infinity. See for instance Bird, Stewart and Lightfoot [1].

The four coefficients satisfy the following:

From Eq. 14a:

$$b_{000,4} + b_{000,2} + b_{000,1} + b_{000,-1} = 0 \quad (15a)$$

From Eq. 14b:

$$4 b_{000,4} + 2 b_{000,2} + b_{000,1} - b_{000,-1} = 0 \quad (15b)$$

From Eq. 14c:

$$b_{000,4} \left(\frac{A}{R}\right)^4 + b_{000,2} \left(\frac{A}{R}\right)^2 + b_{000,1} \left(\frac{A}{R}\right)^1 + b_{000,-1} \left(\frac{A}{R}\right)^{-1} = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{A}{R}\right)^2 \quad (15c)$$

From Eq. 14d:

$$4 b_{000,4} \left(\frac{A}{R}\right)^3 + 2 b_{000,2} \left(\frac{A}{R}\right)^1 + b_{000,1} - b_{000,-1} \left(\frac{A}{R}\right)^{-2} = -\frac{A}{R} \quad (15d)$$

Solution of these linear equations yields the creeping flow stream function as:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_0 = \frac{VR^2}{\Delta_0} \left[\frac{3}{8}(1 + \alpha^{-1})\alpha^{-3} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^4 - \frac{1}{2}(1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2} + \frac{9}{4}\alpha^{-3} + \frac{9}{4}\alpha^{-4}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2 \right. \\ \left. + \frac{3}{4}(1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2} + \alpha^{-3} + \alpha^{-4}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right) - \frac{1}{4}(1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-1} \right] \sin^2 \theta \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{A}{R} \quad (17)$$

$$\Delta_0 = (1 - \alpha^{-1})^3 \left(1 + \frac{7}{4}\alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2}\right) \quad (18)$$

It should be noted that as A increases towards infinity, and as long as the coordinate r remains smaller than A , this solution approaches the classical relationship [1],

$$\psi_{0,Classical} = VR^2 \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2 + \frac{3}{4} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right) - \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-1} \right] \sin^2 \theta \quad (19)$$

The present creeping flow solution, Eq. 16, yields with Eq. 1 a radial velocity with the following characteristics at the downstream stagnation point:

$$v_r = \frac{\partial v_r}{\partial r} = 0 ; \quad \frac{\partial^2 v_r}{\partial r^2} > 0 \quad \text{at } r = R; \theta = 0 \quad (20)$$

The implication is that next to the downstream side of the sphere the axial velocity is positive at least for a small distance, irrespective of the Reynolds number (the other terms of the solution). As the presence of a wake would imply a reversal of the flow in this vicinity, it is concluded that the present relations predict no wake behind the sphere at sufficiently small velocities.

2.2.2. Higher Order Terms

The solution increases rapidly in complexity. The next term is the factor of $(Re/2)$ obtained from substituting Eq. 16 into the right hand side of Eq. 10 and integrating the resulting expression for ψ_1 as described above. Eq. 21 uses decimal notation in the interest of simplicity, and the figures are exact, with no rounding:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_1 = \frac{VR^2 b_{000,1}}{4 \Delta_0 \Delta_1} & \left[(0.5 \alpha^{-3} + 0.625 \alpha^{-4} - 1.125 \alpha^{-5} - 4.375 \alpha^{-6} - 3.75 \alpha^{-7} - 0.5 \alpha^{-8} \right. \\ & - 0.75 \alpha^{-10}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^5 \\ & + (0.75 \alpha^{-3} + 3.75 \alpha^{-4} + 10.5 \alpha^{-5} + 17.8125 \alpha^{-6} + 17.8125 \alpha^{-7} \\ & + 10.5 \alpha^{-8} + 3.75 \alpha^{-9} + 0.75 \alpha^{-10}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^4 \\ & - (1.5 \alpha^{-1} + 4.875 \alpha^{-2} + 10.625 \alpha^{-3} + 19.375 \alpha^{-4} + 33.625 \alpha^{-5} \\ & + 45.375 \alpha^{-6} + 43.25 \alpha^{-7} + 27.5 \alpha^{-8} + 10 \alpha^{-9} + 0.75 \alpha^{-10}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^3 \\ & + (1 + 5 \alpha^{-1} + 15 \alpha^{-2} + 30 \alpha^{-3} + 45 \alpha^{-4} + 59.25 \alpha^{-5} + 68.4375 \alpha^{-6} \\ & + 58.4375 \alpha^{-7} + 32.5 \alpha^{-8} + 11.25 \alpha^{-9} + 2.25 \alpha^{-10}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2 \\ & - (1.5 + 7.5 \alpha^{-1} + 22.5 \alpha^{-2} + 43.125 \alpha^{-3} + 58.125 \alpha^{-4} + 62.625 \alpha^{-5} \\ & + 58.125 \alpha^{-6} + 43.125 \alpha^{-7} + 22.5 \alpha^{-8} + 7.5 \alpha^{-9} + 1.5 \alpha^{-10}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right) + 0.5 \\ & + 6.25 \alpha^{-1} + 19.6875 \alpha^{-2} + 34.1875 \alpha^{-3} + 40.625 \alpha^{-4} + 38.875 \alpha^{-5} \\ & + 29.375 \alpha^{-6} + 16.875 \alpha^{-7} + 8 \alpha^{-8} + 2.5 \alpha^{-9} \\ & - (0.5 + 2.5 \alpha^{-1} + 7.5 \alpha^{-2} + 13.875 \alpha^{-3} + 16.875 \alpha^{-4} + 13.875 \alpha^{-5} \\ & + 7.5 \alpha^{-6} + 2.5 \alpha^{-7} + 0.5 \alpha^{-8}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-1} \\ & + (0.5 + 0.25 \alpha^{-1} + 0.1875 \alpha^{-2} + 2.1875 \alpha^{-3} + 4.375 \alpha^{-4} + 2.625 \alpha^{-5} \\ & \left. - 0.25 \alpha^{-6} - 0.5 \alpha^{-7}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-2} \right] \cos\theta \sin^2\theta \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where

$$b_{000,1} = \frac{3}{4 \Delta_0} (1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2} + \alpha^{-3} + \alpha^{-4}) \quad (22)$$

$$\Delta_1 = 1 + 4 \alpha^{-1} + 10 \alpha^{-2} + \frac{55}{4} \alpha^{-3} + 10 \alpha^{-4} + 4 \alpha^{-5} + \alpha^{-6} \quad (23)$$

2.2.3. Automation

The results in Eqs. 16 and 21 were obtained by tedious and error prone hand calculation. The solution was extended to additional terms by programming a digital computer to perform the arithmetic operations (outlined above) and keep track of the multitude of results, as in a previous series solution of the Navier Stokes equations with the author [2].

The previous contribution carried throughout the calculations a geometric parameter of the flow (degree of curvature of a coiled pipe), and arrived at a general formula for the flow characteristics that included the parameter as a variable [2]. Because of the complexity of the expressions encountered in the present work, its geometric parameter A/R was incorporated only numerically in the computations, directly at the start in boundary conditions 14c and 14d. The final results are sets of coefficients for Eq. 11 for any given value of this parameter.

Computational facilities used for the calculations reported include a personal computer with Microsoft Windows 10 running the 64-bit version of the gfortran Fortran compiler [3] together with the extended precision package MPFUN2020 [4] configured for 400 digits of precision. The latter was found necessary to minimize rounding-off errors in the many operations with numbers of widely varying magnitude.

More than 7,000 coefficients were computed for each A/R in the series solution for the stream function to the twelfth power of the Reynolds number. Table 1 presents overall statistics. Even powers of the Reynolds number are associated with only even powers of $\cos \theta$, and odd powers of the Reynolds number are associated with only odd powers of $\cos \theta$, as noted in the table.

Table 1. Statistics of the Series Solution for the Stream Function

Power of $Re/2$	Highest power of $\cos \theta$	Highest power of $\ln(r/R)$	Highest power of (r/R)	Lowest power of (r/R)
0	0	0	4	-1
1	1 (odds)	0	5	-2
2	2 (evens)	1	8	-3
3	3 (odds)	1	11	-5
4	4 (evens)	2	14	-7
5	5 (odds)	2	17	-9
6	6 (evens)	3	20	-11
7	7 (odds)	3	23	-13
8	8 (evens)	4	26	-15
9	9 (odds)	4	29	-17
10	10 (evens)	5	32	-19
11	11 (odds)	5	35	-21
12	12 (evens)	6	38	-23

Table 2 presents a limited sampling of the results, the coefficients for the stream function for A/R from 100 down to 2, for powers of $(Re/2)$ up to 2. For clarity and compactness, figures are shown in Fortran's exponential format, rounded to four significant digits.

Table 2. Coefficients b_{knji} for the Stream Function, Eq. 11

$A/R=100$			$i = \text{Power of } r/R$											
k	n	j	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3
0	0	0					3.836E-07		-5.115E-01	7.673E-01		-2.558E-01		
1	1	0				9.445E-08	1.472E-07	-2.892E-03	1.962E-01	-2.943E-01	1.053E-01	-9.811E-02	9.378E-02	
2	0	0	-1.464E-15	-2.634E-15	1.763E-09	-1.788E-08	-1.952E-04	3.401E-02	-1.066E+00	1.576E+00	1.532E-02	-5.633E-01	7.105E-03	-3.189E-03
2	0	1					-3.871E-08		-1.204E-01			1.721E-02		-1.434E-03
2	2	0	1.281E-15	5.645E-15	1.534E-08	1.173E-07	-4.944E-04	3.401E-02	-1.079E-01	1.399E-01	-1.059E-01	2.611E-02	3.408E-03	1.093E-02
2	2	1					-7.742E-08					3.441E-02		7.169E-03
$A/R=40$														
0	0	0					6.204E-06		-5.298E-01	7.947E-01		-2.649E-01		
1	1	0				1.492E-06	2.465E-06	-7.553E-03	2.105E-01	-3.157E-01	1.241E-01	-1.052E-01	9.393E-02	
2	0	0	-3.741E-13	-7.138E-13	3.265E-08	-2.864E-07	-5.199E-04	3.867E-02	-2.914E-01	4.094E-01	2.143E-02	-1.832E-01	9.218E-03	-3.664E-03
2	0	1					-6.717E-07		-1.338E-01			1.912E-02		-1.593E-03
2	2	0	3.273E-13	1.530E-12	2.320E-07	1.988E-06	-1.341E-03	3.867E-02	-1.199E-01	1.583E-01	-1.265E-01	3.875E-02	-7.741E-04	1.274E-02
2	2	1					-1.343E-06					3.823E-02		7.965E-03
$A/R=10$														
0	0	0					4.775E-04		-6.439E-01	9.646E-01		-3.212E-01		
1	1	0				1.007E-04	2.303E-04	-3.901E-02	3.106E-01	-4.653E-01	2.507E-01	-1.549E-01	9.759E-02	
2	0	0	-1.943E-09	-5.132E-09	4.325E-06	-2.003E-05	-2.991E-03	7.597E-02	1.107E-01	-2.361E-01	7.106E-02	-3.740E-02	2.628E-02	-7.467E-03
2	0	1					-7.617E-05		-2.396E-01			3.416E-02		-2.844E-03
2	2	0	1.700E-09	1.100E-08	1.080E-05	2.007E-04	-8.493E-03	7.597E-02	-2.147E-01	3.051E-01	-2.918E-01	1.414E-01	-3.518E-02	2.738E-02
2	2	1					-1.523E-04					6.832E-02		1.422E-02
$A/R=4$														
0	0	0					1.157E-02		-1.072E+00	1.579E+00		-5.185E-01		
1	1	0				1.698E-03	9.136E-03	-2.095E-01	8.460E-01	-1.246E+00	8.723E-01	-4.093E-01	1.358E-01	
2	0	0	-7.941E-07	-4.935E-06	2.588E-04	-7.766E-05	-2.034E-02	3.753E-01	6.847E-01	-1.454E+00	4.692E-01	-1.788E-01	1.607E-01	-3.717E-02
2	0	1					-4.945E-03		-1.061E+00			1.477E-01		-1.213E-02
2	2	0	6.949E-07	1.057E-05	-3.841E-04	1.076E-02	-7.593E-02	3.753E-01	-9.547E-01	1.451E+00	-1.596E+00	9.622E-01	-3.153E-01	1.434E-01
2	2	1					-9.890E-03					2.954E-01		6.064E-02
$A/R=2$														
0	0	0					2.647E-01		-4.088E+00	5.471E+00		-1.647E+00		
1	1	0				-2.188E-02	7.240E-01	-4.342E+00	1.118E+01	-1.496E+01	1.109E+01	-4.505E+00	8.338E-01	
2	0	0	2.340E-04	-8.944E-03	5.269E-02	2.866E-01	-8.382E-01	1.822E+01	2.623E+01	-6.176E+01	2.113E+01	-8.561E+00	6.661E+00	-1.415E+00
2	0	1					-1.358E+00		-4.703E+01			5.633E+00		-4.240E-01
2	2	0	-2.048E-04	1.917E-02	-3.082E-01	2.634E+00	-5.615E+00	1.822E+01	-4.323E+01	6.360E+01	-6.989E+01	4.325E+01	-1.428E+01	5.592E+00
2	2	1					-2.716E+00					1.127E+01		2.120E+00

2.2.4. Streamlines

Examples of calculated streamlines are shown in figures 2 through 7, drawn on a plane passing through the center of the sphere, with fluid flowing from left to right. The graph scales are units of R , and only the region inside the imaginary sphere is presented. Detail is expanded closer to the solid sphere.

Fig. 2. Streamlines, creeping flow, $A = 40 R$

Fig. 3. Streamlines, creeping flow, $A = 10 R$

Fig. 6. Streamlines, $A = 10 R$, $Re = 2$

Fig. 7. Streamlines, $A = 4 R$, $Re = 8$

2.3. Discussion

This series solution does not converge at high fluid velocities, specially at high values of the parameter A/R . Testing for convergence was simple: just observing the behavior of the stream function at a certain location when calculated with a variable number of powers of the Reynolds number. For example:

For $A/R = 100$ at $Re = 0.1$ the calculated stream function changes very little in going from powers of Re of 6 through 12 for all locations. At $Re = 0.2$ the values oscillate by a few percent somewhat indefinitely (at least to the twelfth power). Excursions of about 50 percent are observed at $Re = 0.3$, reaching 100 percent and beyond at $Re = 0.4$ and higher.

For $A/R = 40$ at $Re = 0.4$ the calculated stream function converges for all locations. At $Re = 0.5$ there are some oscillations in the values, which reach more than 100 percent at about $Re = 0.8$ and higher

For $A/R = 10$, $Re = 2$ appears close to the upper limit of convergence, which is probably related to the rather pronounced asymmetry of the streamlines in Fig. 6 (upstream vs. downstream). Wide variations are seen at $Re = 3$ and higher.

For $A/R = 4$, $Re = 8$ is close to the upper limit of convergence; rather pronounced asymmetry (upstream vs. downstream) of the streamlines is observed in Fig. 7.

3. Pressure

The equation of motion [1] allows the calculation of the pressure within the fluid in terms of velocity gradients that can be obtained from the stream function. For the present situation there are two equations providing separately the partial derivatives of the pressure with respect to r and with respect to θ . Integration produces the pressure after reconciliation of the various integration constants from both equations.

With the stream function as the power series of Eq. 11, the pressure compensated for the hydrostatic head (modified pressure) becomes a power series in (r/R) , $\ln(r/R)$, $\cos \theta$, and the Reynolds number:

$$\mathcal{P} = p + \rho gh = \frac{\mu V}{R} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{n_L(k)} \sum_{j=0}^{j_L(k,n)} \sum_{i_F(k,n,j)}^{i_L(k,n,j)} p_{knji} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^i \left(\ln \frac{r}{R}\right)^j \cos^n \theta \left(\frac{Re}{2}\right)^k \quad (24)$$

where p_{knji} represent dimensionless constants and n_L, j_L, i_F, i_L are (finite) limits.

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Creeping Flow

Eq. 16 and the equation of motion provide after integration the pressure field for creeping flow as:

$$\mathcal{P}_0 = -\frac{\mu V}{R\Delta_0} \left[\frac{15}{2}(1 + \alpha^{-1})\alpha^{-3} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right) + \frac{3}{2}(1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2} + \alpha^{-3} + \alpha^{-4}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-2} \right] \cos\theta \quad (25)$$

which agrees with the classical expression [1] as A increases towards infinity while r remains less or equal than A .

3.1.2. Higher Order Terms

Higher order terms were calculated for various values of A/R using the expansion for the corresponding stream function (Table 2), with a digital computer performing the arithmetic and recordkeeping. Table 3 shows a few results, up to the square of the Reynolds number. As before, the coefficients are shown in Fortran's exponential format. Zero pressure is set at the point $r = A$, $\theta = \pi/2$.

4. Drag

Forces on the sphere are classified [1] as form drag (derived from pressure) and friction drag (derived from shear stress). The following "drag coefficients" are obtained by direct application of the formulas provided by Bird, Stewart and Lightfoot [1] with the stream function and flow properties presented above. The operations are elaborate and tedious and are not shown here.

$$\text{Drag Coefficient} = C_D = \frac{\text{Drag}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 \pi R^2} \quad (26)$$

4.1 Results

4.1.1. Creeping Flow

The following were obtained analytically from the creeping flow solution presented above:

$$C_{D,Form} = \frac{8}{\Delta_0 \text{Re}} [1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2} + 6\alpha^{-3} + 6\alpha^{-4}] \quad (27)$$

$$C_{D,Friction} = \frac{16(1 - \alpha^{-1})}{\Delta_0 \text{Re}} \left[1 + 2\alpha^{-1} + 3\alpha^{-2} + \frac{3}{2}\alpha^{-3} \right] \quad (28)$$

$$C_{D,Total} = \frac{24}{\Delta_0 \text{Re}} [1 + \alpha^{-1} + \alpha^{-2} + \alpha^{-3} + \alpha^{-4}] \quad (29)$$

Table 3. Coefficients p_{knji} for the Pressure, Eq. 24

$A/R=100$			$i = \text{Power of } r/R$												
k	n	j	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7
0	1	0					-7.672E-06			-1.535E+00					
1	0	0		2.943E-13		2.687E-07	2.943E-07	-2.688E-03	-1.373E-06	-5.887E-01	4.723E-01	-1.962E-01			-3.270E-02
1	2	0		-5.886E-13		-8.062E-07	-3.237E-06		1.766E-06	1.177E+00	-1.417E+00	1.177E+00			-9.811E-02
2	1	0	1.691E-13	2.446E-13	6.628E-08	6.522E-07	-3.640E-05	3.329E-03	-3.011E-01	-2.750E+00	-4.850E-01	-2.043E-01	2.310E-01	2.509E-02	
2	1	1					1.084E-06					2.065E-01			
2	3	0	-3.059E-13	-5.080E-13	-1.060E-07	-1.793E-06	8.129E-07	3.329E-03	1.004E-01	-6.842E-01	8.474E-01	1.799E-01	-4.051E-01	-1.422E-01	9.594E-02
2	3	1										-3.441E-01			
$A/R=40$															
0	1	0					-1.241E-04			-1.589E+00					
1	0	0		7.699E-11		3.871E-06	4.931E-06	-6.201E-03	-2.301E-05	-6.315E-01	5.289E-01	-2.105E-01			-3.508E-02
1	2	0		-1.540E-10		-1.161E-05	-5.424E-05		2.958E-05	1.263E+00	-1.587E+00	1.263E+00			-1.052E-01
2	1	0	4.320E-11	6.628E-11	8.112E-07	1.067E-05	-2.489E-04	9.013E-03	-3.346E-01	-3.728E-01	-5.918E-01	-1.473E-01	2.248E-01	2.788E-02	
2	1	1					1.881E-05					2.294E-01			
2	3	0	-7.818E-11	-1.377E-10	-1.165E-06	-3.014E-05	1.411E-05	9.001E-03	1.115E-01	-7.708E-01	1.012E+00	6.711E-02	-3.759E-01	-1.580E-01	9.952E-02
2	3	1										-3.823E-01			
$A/R=10$															
0	1	0					-9.550E-03			-1.929E+00					
1	0	0		4.560E-07		9.008E-05	4.606E-04	-9.539E-03	-2.147E-03	-9.305E-01	9.152E-01	-3.099E-01			-5.159E-02
1	2	0		-9.120E-07		-2.702E-04	-5.067E-03		2.761E-03	1.861E+00	-2.745E+00	1.859E+00			-1.548E-01
2	1	0	2.244E-07	4.766E-07	-5.198E-05	8.744E-04	-7.228E-03	5.827E-02	-6.008E-01	1.272E+00	-1.451E+00	3.262E-01	1.663E-01	4.977E-02	
2	1	1					2.133E-03					4.099E-01			
2	3	0	-4.061E-07	-9.898E-07	1.612E-04	-2.910E-03	1.600E-03	5.547E-02	2.020E-01	-1.460E+00	2.334E+00	-8.625E-01	-1.223E-01	-2.820E-01	1.254E-01
2	3	1										-6.832E-01			
$A/R=4$															
0	1	0					-2.315E-01			-3.157E+00					
1	0	0		2.679E-04		-1.292E-02	1.827E-02	2.005E-01	-8.402E-02	-2.492E+00	2.856E+00	-8.186E-01			-1.344E-01
1	2	0		-5.358E-04		3.877E-02	-2.010E-01		1.080E-01	4.985E+00	-8.568E+00	4.912E+00			-4.033E-01
2	1	0	9.172E-05	4.582E-04	-1.136E-02	2.413E-02	-2.222E-01	6.686E-01	-2.775E+00	6.482E+00	-8.262E+00	4.272E+00	-4.275E-01	2.122E-01	
2	1	1					1.385E-01					1.772E+00			
2	3	0	-1.660E-04	-9.517E-04	2.862E-02	-1.411E-01	1.038E-01	3.737E-01	1.039E+00	-6.917E+00	1.277E+01	-8.498E+00	2.140E+00	-1.203E+00	2.818E-01
2	3	1										-2.954E+00			
$A/R=2$															
0	1	0					-5.294E+00			-1.094E+01					
1	0	0		1.401E-01		-2.318E+00	1.448E+00	1.079E+01	-6.104E+00	-2.993E+01	3.565E+01	-9.010E+00			-1.356E+00
1	2	0		-2.803E-01		6.953E+00	-1.593E+01		7.848E+00	5.985E+01	-1.070E+02	5.406E+01			-4.069E+00
2	1	0	-2.703E-02	8.305E-01	-4.151E+00	-1.077E+00	-4.128E+01	8.886E+01	-1.486E+02	2.821E+02	-3.641E+02	2.151E+02	-3.504E+01	7.420E+00	
2	1	1					3.803E+01					6.760E+01			
2	3	0	4.892E-02	-1.725E+00	1.152E+01	-2.994E+01	2.852E+01	-6.252E+00	7.815E+01	-3.152E+02	5.591E+02	-4.111E+02	1.234E+02	-4.205E+01	5.493E+00
2	3	1										-1.127E+02			

4.1.2. Higher Terms

Table 4 presents results for the drag coefficient for various values of the parameter A/R in the form of coefficients for the expression:

$$C_D = \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} c_k \left(\frac{\text{Re}}{2} \right)^k \quad (30)$$

Only even powers k contribute to the drag in this expansion. Again, Fortran's exponential format is used in the presentation.

Table 4. Coefficients c_k for the Drag Coefficient, Eq. 30

$A/R=100$	$k = \text{Power of } (\text{Re}/2)$			
Type	0	2	4	6
Form	8.184E+00	1.858E+01	-8.754E+02	6.473E+04
Friction	1.637E+01	3.678E+01	-1.748E+03	1.293E+05
Total	2.455E+01	5.536E+01	-2.624E+03	1.940E+05
$A/R=40$				
Form	8.477E+00	6.337E+00	-4.629E+01	5.188E+02
Friction	1.695E+01	1.230E+01	-9.176E+01	1.029E+03
Total	2.543E+01	1.864E+01	-1.380E+02	1.548E+03
$A/R=10$				
Form	1.034E+01	1.028E+00	-3.787E-01	2.102E-01
Friction	2.053E+01	1.737E+00	-6.698E-01	3.703E-01
Total	3.087E+01	2.765E+00	-1.049E+00	5.805E-01
$A/R=4$				
Form	1.807E+01	2.819E-01	-9.413E-03	4.817E-04
Friction	3.244E+01	3.203E-01	-1.120E-02	5.600E-04
Total	5.052E+01	6.022E-01	-2.061E-02	1.042E-03
$A/R=2$				
Form	8.659E+01	1.323E-01	-2.924E-04	1.001E-06
Friction	8.847E+01	6.596E-02	-1.570E-04	5.403E-07
Total	1.751E+02	1.982E-01	-4.494E-04	1.542E-06

4.2. Discussion

The creeping flow results for the drag coefficient agree with the classic Stokes formula for large values of the parameter A . In the series expansion the drag coefficient does not converge for high Reynolds numbers, in particular at high values of A , similar to the conditions described for the stream function.

5. Dedication

This work is dedicated to my wife Kim.

6. References

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4. D.H. Bailey, *MPFUN2020: A new thread-safe arbitrary precision package*, <http://www.davidhbailey.com/dhbpapers/mpfun2020.pdf>, downloaded 04-02-2021.